

Effects of E-payment System on Corrupt Practice in Nigerian Public Sector: An Empirical Investigation

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of e-payment on corrupt practices in the public sector of the Nigerian economy. The aim was to empirically investigate the effects of digital payment given the contradictory opinions regarding effectiveness in addressing the issue of corrupt practice (embezzlement of public funds) by public officials in Nigeria. Data for the study were collected primarily through questionnaires administered to 400 purposively selected respondents from state ministries in Kogi, Adamawa, Ebonyi, Delta, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Analysis of the data was done using descriptive, correlation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistics. It was found that the various components of the digital payment system used in Nigeria namely: Point of sale, smart card, mobile payment, debit card, and remita (explanatory variables of the study) have a significant effect on corrupt practice dependent variable proxied by embezzlement of public fund. The F-statistics values for all the explanatory variables greater than 1.96 for a two-tailed test at a 5 percent significant level indicate that the usage/deployment of e-payment has a significant effect on corrupt practice in terms of reducing the rate at which public funds are embezzled. The study concluded with the recommendation that efforts to encourage digital systems for the receipt and payment of cash in the Nigerian public sector should be sustained to ensure compliance by all tiers of government. This is important because of the low rate at which the payment is embraced at the local government level.

Keywords: E-payment, Corrupt practice, Embezzlement, Public officials, Public fund

Word count: 242

Introduction

The recent global reforms in the public sector accounting process are to ensure transparency in the management of public Management (NPM) is the e-payment system that has taken deep root in many advanced nations such as the UK, USA, and New Zealand. The payment system has been seen as a major way to salvage economies from economic doldrums and the quagmire of corruption that usually thrives in public sector operations (Hersla & Fisher, 2016). The thriving of the illicit act is premised on the belief of government officials especially those entrusted with the responsibility of managing public funds that the sector belongs to no one. The erroneous beliefs of ownership of public sector institutions and organizations have on many occasions led those in charge of the management of public funds to disregard extant rules and regulations governing the funds in most cases for personal gains (Porter & Butten, 2015). The personal gain embodied in corruption not only depletes the common resources of the citizens but also demeans the overall image of a nation with all manners of consequences.

In Nigeria, Government has taken various measures and reforms to address cases of corruption particularly in the public sector. Prominent among the anti-corruption measures is the establishment of institutions such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Independent Corrupt Practices and other related offense Commission (ICPC), and policies such as Bank Verification Number (BVN) for all accounts, Treasury Single Account (TSA) and e-payment system for payment and collection of cash in public sector organizations in compliance with what obtains globally.

In support of the efficiency of the e-payment system in reducing corrupt practices in public organizations in Nigeria, studies (Onyiabor & Wulama, 2017; Uronme & Julius, 2018 and Nweneli & Meniyi, 2019) in theoretical analysis stated that there is a reduction in corrupt cases in the Nigerian Public Sector as a result of the operation of e-payment system. Similarly in the view of Igundi (2021) opined that the scores of Nigeria in the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) reported by Transparency International have greatly improved for better of which e-payment system in the Nigerian Public sector is a major contributing factor. On the contrary, Molokwu and Ogwuta (2021) in their separate views on corrupt practices in the public sector in the Nigerian economy stated that the illegal practice has worsened despite all measures to curb the menace. Reaffirming the views Eribara (2023) stated that efforts to address corruption in the Nigerian public has not yielded the much-needed results as the practice is getting worse in the country, especially at the local government level where there is not much compliance with government auto-corruption measure, especially the e-payment system.

These contradictory views about the effectiveness of the e-payment system in curbing corrupt practices in the public sector of Nigeria are theoretical assertions that have not been empirically investigated. The objective of this study, therefore, is to empirically test the effect of the e-payment system on corrupt practices in the Nigerian public sector.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Conceptual Review

E-payment System: The payment system refers to ways of making transactions or paying bills online or through electronic mediums without the use of physical cheques or cash (Ducker & Chentro, 2016). The payment system works for the convenience of users. Speed, time-saving, and safety of transactions are some of the advantages of the payment system compared to the traditional payment and receipt of cash which is proven to be manipulations and misappropriation (Wright & Brown, 2017). The electronic medium of making and receiving payment has many types of which the major ones according to Leonard and Blikern (2016) are debit/ credit cards, e-wallets, bank-to-bank transfers, prepaid vouchers, and power cash. The most commonly used one in Nigeria according to Omotola (2023) is bank-to-bank transfer. Bank-to-Bank (B2B) transfers are real-time bank transfers from one bank to another (Gorrester & Hashber, 2016). The transfers enable the beneficiary to receive payment online and instantly. The B2B transfer also known as external transfer is the process of getting funds from one account to another without the use of cash (Nabta & Behn, 2017). The transfer involves the utilization of the internet to expedite getting money from one account to another thus eliminating the need to move cash between banks. The five most commonly used B2B transfers in Nigeria according to Omotola (2023) are the point of sale, smart card, mobile pay, debit card and remita.

Point of Sale (POS): It is a financial transaction that occurs online with receipts for a payment generated either in print or electronically (Mastow & Bonnel, 2017). POS operation helps individuals to make payments electronically without the involvement of physical cash. The payment platform enables users to make B2B payments without having to carry cash around.

Smart Card (SC): The e-payment enabling card is a contactless payment and a wireless financial transaction that makes it possible for the user to make payment without physical cash. Payment via wireless chips embedded in the payment card enables financial transaction that does not require cash (Morphy & Dreelin, 2018).

Mobile Payment (MP): A mobile payment is a transfer or payment of funds to a person or organization using a mobile device to execute and confirm the payment (Spencer & Parkley, 2015). Near-Field Communication (NFC), Sound waves-based payments, Magnetic Secure Transmission (MST), Mobile Wallets, Quick Response (QR), and code payments are some of the types of mobile electronic payments. In Nigeria, the best mobile payment system is Naira.com designed by Charmsswitch, a top fintech company in the country (Okota & George, 2021). Naira.com allows users to send and receive funds, pay bills, and even make donations to non-profit organizations such as public institutions, ministries, and agencies of government.

Debit Card (DC): DC allows payment of money by drawing on funds one has in his/her bank account. DC requires users to pay now (immediately) as the card pulls money directly from the user's account for payment. A debit card also known as a bank card is a payment card that is used in place of cash to make payment (Gan & Roly, 2016). Fast, easy, convenient, and secure payment are some of the advantages of a debit card.

Remita (RmT): It is an innovative way to manage electronic payments, collections, employee payrolls, and schedules which encompasses all banks (Ertzen & Photepal, 2018). The platform is an e-payment system that delivers payment instructions to accounts in banks online and in real time. The electronic payment system allows people and organizations to process intricate and complex financial transactions while being initiative and simple (Whinesky, 2018).

Introduced by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) and implemented by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the payment platform is recognized by Nigerian banks as a valid means of electronic payment. Numerous advantages of RMT according to Clark Roggs (2019) account checking in all banks with simple RMT login, paying one or multiple beneficiaries at once in all banks, the ability to trace expenses to ascertain spending patterns, and the ability to view the progress of any transaction every step of the way. It is a secured electronic payment system that helps individuals and organizations receive payments, pay bills and manage their finances across multiple banks in real time (Hercker & Lodzy, 2019).

Corruption Practice (CP): The concept as it relates to the management of public funds is misappropriation or outright embezzlement of public money. CP especially in public sector institutions in terms of the application of finances is financial fraud where a person or group of persons diverts or divert money that was entrusted to his/her or for purposes

other than what the money was meant (Setlo & Bridly, 2018). It is a criminal act- where someone mostly in connivance with some people either within or outside his or her organization steals or misappropriates money entrusted in his/her care to manage or safeguard. It is a criminal case of defalcation where public funds are diverted for personal benefits (Conny & Spicer, 2017). Thus, Nordiner (2020) viewed CP in terms of money held in a fiduciary capacity as embezzlement of money or the crime of secretly taking money that is in one's care.

Empirical Review

In Italy, Bornner and Linds (2018) examined the effect of the e-payment system on the management of funds in public establishments. Data for the study were obtained from responses to questionnaires administered to 127 officials in public institutions. The results of the descriptive analysis indicated a correlation between increased income generation and the e-payment system. In Cambodia, Jones and Desmond, (2017) did a study on the effects of e-payment on government revenue growth. Results of correlation analysis of responses to a questionnaire administered to 400 randomly selected public officials in the country. Results indicated that there is a positive relationship between revenue growth and an e-payment system for the collection and receipt of cash.

Pursham and Karmara (2020) provided evidence on the e-payment system and employee behaviour in public organizations in India. The study investigated the relationship between the e-payment system and the attitude of employees toward embezzlement. Data for the study were obtained primarily from responses to a questionnaire administered to 37 public officials purposively selected to reflect the characteristics desired by the researchers. Results of correlation and descriptive analysis indicated that the e-payment system is associated with a low level of embezzlement in public organizations.

In the UK, Thomas and Cole (2022) examined the relationship between electronic payment of taxes, transparency, and the level of corruption of public authorities. Data for the study were primarily obtained from responses from 450 officials in different public establishments. Results of correlation analysis showed a positive and significant relationship between digital payment systems, transparency, and the growth of public revenue. The funding suggests that e-payment is a key antidote to corrupt practices of embezzlement of public funds.

Werd and Budney (2022) studied the effects of digital payment systems on the transparency and performance of public entities in Singapore. Data for the study were

primarily obtained through a questionnaire administered to 260 respondents randomly selected from 15 public organizations. Results of Pearson correlation analysis indicated a positive relationship between the e-payment system, transparency, and performance of the entities using revenue growth as a proxy for performance.

In Nigeria, Dapel and Lazurus (2019) examined the effects of anti-corruption and financial reforms on transparency and governance in Plateau State. The aim was to examine the impact of three financial reforms namely: Single Account (TSA), Bank Verification Number (BVN), and whistle-blowing on transparency in the management of public funds. Data for the study were generated from the responses to a questionnaire administered to 420 respondents made up of randomly selected staff of the state ministries. Results of ANOVA, Chi-Square, Standard deviation, and T-statistics revealed that while the operation of TSA and BVN exactly a significant positive impact on transparency in the management of public finances that of whistle-blowing is non-significant.

In Edo state, Okota & George (2021) carried out a study on the impact of the government's financial policy on corrupt practice detection. The aim was to ascertain the efficacy of TSA, BVN, and the operation of the Nigerian Inter-Bank Security System (NIBSS) in curbing corrupt practices it was an exploratory study that made use of the primary source for data collection. Responses to the questionnaire administered to purposively selected 345 respondents made up of bank officials and civil servants in the states were analysed using regression. Results indicated that the use of reforms and technology has impacted positively in curbing corruption in the state.

Similarly in Lagos, Salawudeen and Taju (2022) studied the effects of BVN and the adoption of TSA on transparency and governance in Lagos state. The authors utilized primary sources to obtain data from a sample of 1650 respondents from public establishments in the state. Analysis of data was done using correlation and multiple regressions. Results indicated that the adoption of these financial reforms has positively impacted curbing corrupt practices in the management of public funds in the state.

A review of previous studies showed a dearth of empirical research on the e-payment system and its effects on corrupt practices in the public sector of Nigeria. Few studies (Dapel & Lazurus, 2019; Okota & George; 2021; Sanni, et al 2021) focused on the impact of government financial reforms/ policy particularly the operation of TSA, BVW, and NIBSS on corrupt practices in Nigeria. Therefore, this study on an empirical investigation of e-payment systems specifically the effects of the operation of the five recognized digital

payments namely; POS, SC, MP, DC, and RmT on Corrupt practice (embezzlement of public funds) is a contribution of this study to existing knowledge given the existence of divergent views about the effect of the digital payment system in curbing corrupt practice in the Nigerian public sector. The divergent opinions provided the basis for the hypotheses of the study formulated as follows:

- Ho₁: POS e-payment system does not affect corrupt practices in the Nigerian public sector.
- Ho₂: SC e-payment system does not affect corrupt practices in the Nigerian public sector.
- Ho₃: MP e-payment system does not affect corrupt practices in the Nigerian public sector.
- Ho₄: DC e-payment system has no effect on corrupt practice in the Nigerian public sector
- Ho₅: RmT e-payment system has no effect on corrupt practice in the Nigerian public sector.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the collective action theory of corruption. The theory was propounded by Mancur Olson in 1965 as an alternative explanation for why systematic corruption persists despite laws and anti-corruption efforts in some countries. Persson and Teorell (2013) regard systematic corruption as a social norm that everyone in society will start seeing the illicit act simply as the normal way to get things done. As a social norm, people will despise the negative consequences of corruption and still engage in the act as they believe that it doesn't make sense to be the only honest person in a corrupt system (Peiffer & Marquette, 2015). Therefore, the mentality and absurdity of being the only honest man in a corrupt society pave for an institution or organizational culture of corruption that leads to the normalization of corrupt practices at the individual as well as the societal level.

To combat corruption, the theory suggests the need for coordinated approaches such as anti-corruption reforms and coordinated efforts of government as well as society (collective action) to address the issue of corruption.

The relevance of the theory to this study is grounded on its suggestion as it is research on the effects of the efforts of the Nigerian government to solve the corrupt practice of embezzlement of public funds in Nigerian society.

Data and Methods

Data for the study were collected primarily through a structured questionnaire designed

by the researcher. The questionnaire was administered to purposively selected 400 respondents made up of staff in accounts and finance departments in federal and state ministries in Kogi, Adamawa, Ebonyi, Delta states, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) for their opinion on the questionnaire constructs. The questionnaires were designed to reflect five (5) point Likert scale. Out of the 400 questionnaires distributed, 350 were correctly filled and returned representing approximately 88 percent responses rate. The analysis of the collected responses was done using descriptive statistics, correlation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for the effect of each of the components of e-payment on corrupt practices in the Nigerian public sector.

Model Specification

The model is to establish the relationship between the predictor variables ($X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4,$ and X_5) represented by POS, SC, MP, DC, and RmT and Corrupt practices proxied by Embezzlement of Public Fund (EPF) is depicted in the following equations:

$$EPF = f(POS, SC, MA, DC, RmT) \text{ ----- Equation 1}$$

Imputing the coefficient of the variables:

$$EPF = a + \beta_1 POS + \beta_2 SC + \beta_3 MP + \beta_4 DC + \beta_5 RmT + E \text{ ----- Equation 2}$$

Where

EPF = Embezzlement of Public Fund, a = Intercept, POS = Point of Sale, SC = Smart Card, MP = Mobile Pay, DC = Debit Card, RmT = Remita and $\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Coefficient of the explanatory variables

The assumed positive sign of the coefficient represents the apriori expectation of a positive trend among the predictor variables of the study.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

Variable	Measurement	Source
EPF	Measured by the rated responses to the questionnaire construct on the variable	Harris & Lington (2016), Gregg & Jones (2016)
POS	Measured by the extent to which embezzlement of the public fund has been reduced occasioned by the use of POS to make payment according to the rated responses to the questionnaire construct on the variable	Oliver & Dudley (2014) Gerron & Neberger (2015)
SC	Measured by the rated responses to the questionnaire on the extent to which the use of SC has reduced or eliminated access to cash and embezzlement of public funds by government officials	Khilbern & Romplan (2015), Krane & Roggers (2016)
MP	Measured by the rated responses on the extent to which the use of mobile payment has reduced access to cash and embezzlement of public funds	Marrat & Bnott (2014) Ornord & Limms (2015)
DC	Measured by the rated responses to the questionnaire on the extent to which the use of DC for payment has reduced access to cash	Roddler & Lursby (2015)

RmT	Measured by the extent to which the use of remita for payment has reduced access to cash and embezzlement of public funds by government officials according to the responses to the questionnaire constructed on the variable	Spencer & Parley (2015) Dreger & Pemski (2016)
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Source: Field survey 2023

Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 2 presents the results of the descriptive analysis of the study. The absence of outliers in the data set was confirmed by low values of the Skewness and Kurtosis for all the variables. Acceptable values for normality distribution for skewness range between -3 to +3 and for kurtosis, the value fall between -10 to +10 (Olasu & Udebi, 2015). The values of the skewness for this study range between 0.0045 to 0.683 and for kurtosis the values fall between 1.445 and 2.789. The normality of the distribution was further confirmed by the positive values of the Jarque-Bera test statistics values that are close to Zero (0). The Jarque-bera values for the study fall between 0.054 and 0.064. The absence of outliers and normality of the data from the skewness, kurtosis, and Jarque-bera statistics values confirms the suitability of data for generalization (Olasu & Udebi, 2015).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics – Summary of Normality Statistics

	EPF	POS	SC	MP	DC	RmT
Mean	3.947000	3.83928	3.83928	3.625600	3.354950	3.647932
Median	4.109600	3.810400	3.810400	3.520000	3.493160	3.619880
Maximum	4.400000	4.400000	4.400000	4.400000	4.400000	4.400000
Minimum	3.100000	3.100000	3.100000	3.100000	3.100000	3.100000
Std. Dev	0.379858	0.445149	0.404862	0.301649	0.360865	0.356112

Skewness	0.048113	0.461273	0.584663	0.683466	0.045707	0.438209
Kurtosis	1.445264	2.289049	2.786554	2.146441	2.229243	1.931797
Jarque bera	- 0.064424	0.172262	0.135056	0.125445	0.054022	0.075267
Profitability	0.050455	0.051703	0.047861	0.074841	0.056337	0.068928
Sum	43.41926	42.24000	42.24000	42.24000	39.88160	42.24000
Sum. Sq.Dev	1.639200	2.251793	1.862657	1.034000	1.557240	2.139203
Observation	25	25	25	25	25	25

Source: Author's Computation 2023

Table 3 presents the results of the correlation analysis. It is revealed from the table that a positive relationship exists between the e-payment system and corrupt practices in terms of the reduction of embezzlement of public funds by government officials entrusted with the responsibility of managing public funds. The values of EPF (0.5815, 0.6260, 0.3134, 0.2955, and 0.6197) for POS, SC, MP, DC, and RmT respectively shown on the matrix are indicative of the effects of these variables on corrupt practice in terms of reduction of public fund embezzlement. This finding is consistent with previous studies (Bornner & Linds, 2018; Pursham & Karma, 2020; Thomas & Cole, 2022; Werd & Budney, 2022) that found in their studies of the positive effects of the e-payment system on corrupt practices. The finding is also in line with studies (Okota & George, 2021 and Oyeyemi & Lasis, 2022) that found in their studies the positive effect of financial reforms of government and anti-corruption policies on transparency in management of public funds.

Table 3: Relationship between e-payment system and corrupt practice in the Nigerian public sector

	EPF	POS	SC	MP	DC	RmT
EPF	1.000					
POS	0.5815	1.000				
SC	0.6260	0.6147	1.000			
MP	0.3134	0.0731	0.5974	1.000		
DC	0.2955	0.8164	0.6273	0.7472	1.000	
RmT	0.6197	0.4351	0.5803	0.6605	0.7262	1.000

Source: Authors Computation 2023

From Table 4, it is indicated that the e-payment system deployed in the receipt and collection of money in the public sector of Nigeria has a positive effect on the corrupt practice of embezzlement of money. The positive impact/effect implies a reduction in the level of embezzlement of public money due to the restriction of access to physical cash. Further, since the F-statistics values of 7.38, 8.08, 10.71, 15.66, and 8.49 for POS, SC, MP, DC, and RmT respectively are greater than 1.96 for a two-tailed test at a 5 percent significant level, therefore, the null hypotheses of the study are rejected. The rule of thumb is to reject the null hypothesis of a study if the calculated F-statistics value is greater than the critical value (Olasu & Udebi, 2015). The rejection of the null hypothesis implies that there is a significant relationship between the predictor variables and the response variable. The positive effect and the relationship were further confirmed by the values of the coefficient of determination (R^2). The R^2 value of 0.4732 47 indicated the combined effects of the predictor variables on the response variable/dependent variable. The result implies that an approximately, 47 percent reduction in the level at which public funds are embezzled by officials in the Nigerian public sector is accounted for by the deployment of an e-payment system. The funding is consistent with studies (Onyiabor & Wulama, 2017; Uronme & Julius, 2018; Nweneli & Meniyi, 2019) and contrary to the views of Molokwu and Ogwuta (2021) and Onabisi and Rhode (2022).

Table 4: ANOVA: Analysis of the Effect of E -payment System on Corrupt Practice in the Nigerian Public Sector

Source	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Prob>F
Model	202.81492	349	7.800574	198.14	0.000
EPF	8.8018674	4	2.200467	58.75	0.000
POS	1.1060520	4	1.276513	7.38	0.003
SC	5.7045206	4	1.426130	8.08	0.021
MA	1.9628142	2	0.401093	10.71	0.000
DC	2.3472939	2	0.586823	15.66	0.000
RmT	1.2723288	4	0.318082	8.49	0.000
Residual	12.162845	351	0.032962		

R. Squared = 0.4732 Adjusted R. Squared = 0.4614

Source: Computation using SPSS

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study examined the effect of the e-payment system on corrupt practices in the Nigerian public sector. Data for the study were obtained from responses to a questionnaire administered to 400 staff from state ministries across all the geopolitical zones of the country and the FCT. Analysis of the data was done using descriptive, as well as correlation, and ANOVA statistics. Findings indicated that the e-payment system (electronic system) for the collection and payment of cash has a positive effect on corrupt practices in terms of a decrease in the level of embezzlement of public funds in Nigeria. It is therefore recommended that efforts to completely ensure e-payment systems are deployed in receipt and payment of cash in public institutions and establishments are sustained should be encouraged. This is because of the low rate at which the digital payment system is embraced in the Nigerian public sector, especially at the local government levels.

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